

PERCEPTION OF THE TEACHERS TOWARDS THE PROBLEMS FACED IN IMPLEMENTATION OF EVALUATION REFORMS IN HARYANA

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Abstract

After the independence a lot of evaluation reforms have been undertaken on the basis of important recommendations suggested by the various commissions and committees. The main reforms introduced in the evaluation system in school education are CCE, grading system and semester system. Although Haryana Board has introduced evaluation reforms in terms of CCE, grading system and semester system, however the teachers, parents and students are facing certain problem in understanding of these evaluation reforms. The present study was based on the perception of the teachers towards the problem faced in implementation of evaluation reforms in Haryana. The objectives of the present study were to find out the perception of the teachers towards problem faced in implementation of evaluation reforms (CCE, Grading System and Semester System). A descriptive survey method was used for the research. The sample comprised of 120 teachers of secondary school (60 from Govt. and 60 from private schools) of Bahadurgarh block of Jhajjar district in Haryana. For the present study a self-made questionnaire for teachers were developed to test the following objectives: a) to find out the perception of the teachers towards problems faced in implementation of CCE .b) to find out the perception of teachers towards problem faced in implementation of grading system. c) To find out the perception of teachers towards problem faced in implementation of semester system. The study revealed that most of the teachers were facing problems in implementation of evaluation reforms in Haryana.

Keywords: Teachers' perception, Evaluation reforms (CCE, grading system & semester system), Secondary school teachers, Haryana.

Introduction

"The highest education is that which does not merely gives us information but makes our life harmony with all existences."

.....*Rabindranath Tagore*

Education, in general, aims at shaping the personality of children in the desired direction. It is a complex concept that refers to both the process and the product. Education is the process of development, which consist of the passage of the human being from infancy to adulthood. It is a holistic process and not only the training of the intellect. It is done through a variety of inputs like curriculum textbooks and other instructional materials, organization of teaching learning through direct or indirect contact with children. Education is essentially a social affair and not an isolated activity. It is related to life and community. Everyone those who are involved in education from school administration to parents and teachers as well as all other stakeholders' wants to ensure that the educational programs in which they are involved are achieving their stated goals. In this context evaluation measures the achievement of students to know how much and how well they are achieving the pre-set objectives. It provides an essential yardstick to judge the quality of students. It plays an important role in the overall educational system. Education should not be restricted within the boundaries of marks, percentage, ranks, positions and academic scores. There is an urgent need to eradicate the existing pressure on children to grow in stress free environment. So the teachers and the parents have to understand their inner feeling and requirements.

Significance

Following the recommendation of NCF 2005, Haryana was the first State in the country to implement evaluation reforms in terms of CCE, grading system and semester system from the year 2006-07. Many stakeholders particularly teachers have faced problems in implementation of these reforms. The present study presumes that success of any innovation in the field of education greatly depends upon its proper implementation by the practitioners. The practitioners need to utilize the new knowledge through continuous personal striving towards greater proficiency (Ramdas, 2001). Effective implementation of these reforms, therefore requires the teachers to acquire sound knowledge about the system and are to be trained in making accurate observations and to appropriately modifying the teaching-learning environment. It is therefore pertinent to find out teachers' perception towards the problems faced in implementation of evaluation reforms in Haryana.

Problems Related to Implementation of Present Scheme of Evaluation							
S. No.	STATEMENTS		SA	A	U	D	SD
1.	It is easy to evaluate the scholastic aspects of the students.	F	24	45	10	25	16
		P	20	37.5	8.3	20.83	13.3
2.	It is difficult to evaluate the co-scholastic aspects of the students	F	61	40	12	6	1
		P	50.8	33.3	10	5	0.8
3.	Sometimes the syllabus is neglected due to heavy examination load	F	16	62	19	23	0
		P	13.3	51.6	15.8	18.3	0
4.	Subjectivity is not the major problem in awarding internal grades to the student	F	19	55	19	23	4
		P	15.8	45.83	15.8	19.16	3.3
5	The present scheme of evaluation has increased the work load of the teachers.	F	35	62	12	11	0
		P	29.2	51.6	10	9.16	0
6	Checking of so many projects, worksheets & assignments is stressful for teachers						
		F	36	47	17	13	7
7	The present scheme of evaluation has increased the work load of the students	P	30	39.16	14.1	10.8	5.8
					6		
		P	33.33	37.5	10	19.16	0
8	In present scheme of evaluation, students do not get enough time for self-study	F	40	45	12	23	0
		P	33.33	37.5	10	19.16	0
9	Ensuring healthy competition among the students is a difficult task in the present scheme of evaluation.	F	30	48	18	19	5
		P	25	40	15	15.8	4.16
10	Monitoring the changes taking place in	F	40	49	13	12	6

	the child's behavior is a difficult task in the present scheme of evaluation	P	33.3	40.8	10.8 3	10	5
11	Books are not designed according to the semester wise courses.	F	23	82	6	9	0
		P	19.16	68.3	5	7.5	0
12.	Providing continuous feedback to the students every time is a difficult task in the resent scheme of evaluation.	F	14	64	18	24	0
		P	11.6	53.3	15	20	0
13.	Filling and preparing records of the students is the most time consuming activity for the teachers.	F	32	63	16	9	0
		P	26.6	52.5	13.3	7.5	0
14	Providing remedial instruction to students is a difficult task according to present evaluation system.	F	18	75	20	8	2
		P	15	62.5	16.6	6.66	1.66
15	Preparing CCE report cards is a lengthy and time consuming process.	F	43	59	9	9	0
		P	35.8	49.1		P	35.8
16	School teachers have tension of student's result due to grading system	F	25	45	20	28	2
		P	20.8	37.5	16.6	23.3	1.66
17	Students show artificial behavior in front of teachers to get good grades in the activities.	F	26	58	13	23	0
		P	21.6	48.3	10.8 3	19.16	0
18	Giving grades to the students on the basis of their performance is a difficult task for teachers.	F	19	50	15	34	2
		P	15.8	41.6	12.5	28.3	1.66
19	The syllabus of all school subjects is not divided into units according to semester wise work load	F	23	75	16	6	0
		P	19.16	62.5	13.3	5	0
20	The high student teacher ratio is a big problem in implementing the present scheme of evaluation	F	34	49	5	30	2
		P	28.33	40.8	4.16	25	1.66
21	Inappropriate school facilities are a big problem in implementing CCE system in schools	F	55	45	10	7	3
		P	45.8	37.5	8.33	5.83	2.5
22	Due to co-scholastic activities, the reading habits of the students are dying out day by day	F	14	60	24	20	2
		P	11.6	50	20	16.6	1.66

23	Rigid time table of schools is a hurdle in implementing the present scheme of evaluation.	F	42	55	15	8	0
		P	35	45.8	12.5	6.66	0
24	Lack of orientation of parents is a big issue in implementing the present scheme of evaluation in schools	F	30	37	23	29	1
		P	25	30.8	19.16	24.16	0.8
25	The present scheme of evaluation has helped me in better understanding about the students	F	0	17	10	70	23
		P	0	14.1	8.3	58.3	19.16
26	The present scheme of evaluation has helped me in effective classroom management	F	8	10	6	65	31
		P	6.6	8.3	5	54.16	25.8
27	The present scheme of evaluation has helped me in improving my efficiency to teach	F	14	32	12	51	13
		P	11.6	26.6	10	42.5	10.8
28	The present scheme of evaluation has helped me in better organization and transaction of the subject-matter	F	4	23	17	65	11
		P	3.3	19.16	14.1	54.16	9.16
29	Due to the present scheme of evaluation the students are more inclined towards co-scholastic areas	F	25	60	11	14	10
		P	20.8	50	9.16	11.6	8.3
30	Due to the present scheme of evaluation malpractices like paper leakage has reduced	F	36	14	10	45	15
		P	30	11.6	8.3	37.5	12.5

Interpretation:

From the table it was found that 57% teachers agree that it is easy to evaluate the scholastic aspects of the students and 84% teachers agree that it is difficult to evaluate the co-scholastic aspects of the students. Around 63% teachers agree that sometimes the syllabus is neglected by them due to heavy examination load and around 62% teachers agree that subjectivity is not the major problem in awarding internal grades to the students. It was also found that around 81% teachers agree that the present scheme of evaluation has increased the work load of the teachers, around 69% of the teachers agree that checking of so many projects, worksheets and assignments is stressful for them and around 71% teachers agree that the present scheme of the evaluation has also increased the workload of the students and they do not get enough time for self-study. It is evident from the above table that around 60% of the teachers agree that ensuring healthy competition among the students and 74% said that monitoring the changes taking place in the child's behavior is a difficult task in the present scheme of evaluation. Around 87% of the teachers agree that the books are not designed according to the semester wise courses. It is found that around 65% teachers agree that providing continuous feedback to the students every time is a difficult task and 79% teachers agree that filling and preparing records of the students is the most

time consuming activity for the teachers. It is revealed from the above table that around 77% of the teachers agree that providing remedial instructions to the students is difficult and preparing CCE report cards is a lengthy and time consuming process. Around 58.3% of the teachers agree that the school teachers have tension of student's result due to grading system and giving grades to them on the basis of their performance is difficult for teachers as the students show artificial behavior in front of teachers to get good grades in the activities, assignments and projects. Around 57% teachers agree that giving grades to the students on the basis of their performance is a difficult task for teachers and around 80% teachers agree that the syllabus of all subjects is not divided into units according to semester wise work load and high student- teacher ratio, inappropriate school facilities rigid time table of schools are a big problem in implementing CCE system in schools. More than 50% teachers agree that due to Co-scholastic activities, the reading habits of the students are dying out day by day and lack of orientation of parents is a big issue in implementing the present scheme of evaluation in schools. It was also found that 50% teachers disagree that the present scheme of evaluation has helped in better understanding of the students, in effective classroom management, in improving their efficiency to teach, and in better organization and transaction of the subject-matter. Around 70% of teachers agree that due to the present scheme of evaluation students are more inclined towards co-scholastic areas and 50% teachers disagree that due to the present evaluation scheme of evaluation malpractices like paper leakage has reduced.

Table : Mean of Responses of Teachers

Problems Related to Implementation of Present Scheme of Evaluation					
	SA	A	U	D	SD
Mean	26.93	49.2	14.4	24.4	5.23

Figure 1.2 Mean of Teachers' Responses regarding Problems in Implementation of Present Scheme of Evaluation

Table 1.2 and Figure 1.1 shows that mean of responses of teachers regarding present scheme of evaluation is 26.93 for strongly agree, 49.2 for agree, 14.4 for undecided, 24.4 for

disagree and 5.23 for strongly disagree .The table shows that most of the teachers are facing problems in Implementation of present scheme of evaluation.

Discussion:

On the basis of the analysis and interpretation of the perception of the teachers related to the problems faced by them in implementation of evaluation reforms in Haryana it can be concluded that most of the teachers agree that sometimes the syllabus is neglected by them due to heavy examination load and the workload of the teachers has increased. It is found that most of the teachers agree that students do not get enough time for self-study and ensuring healthy competition among the students and providing remedial instructions to the students is a difficult task and the high student- teacher ratio is a big problem in implementing the present scheme of evaluation. Most of the teachers agree that due to co-scholastic activities, the reading habits of the students are dying out day by day and the rigid time table of the school is a hurdle in implementing the present scheme of evaluation and also the books are not designed according to the semester wise courses. Most of the teachers agree to this that filling and preparing records of the students is the most time consuming activity for teachers and students show artificial behavior in front of teachers to get good grades in activities, assignments and projects, and it is also found that most of the teachers agree that preparing CCE report card is a lengthy and time consuming process and most of the teachers also agree that the syllabus of all subjects is not divided into units according to semester wise workload. Similarly studies conducted by Padhi, S.K(2010), Bhattacharjee and Sharma(2009), Y. Sreekanth (2006) revealed that the teachers had moderate positive perception towards CCE and various problems perceived by teachers such as heavy workload, improper training for CCE implementation, overcrowded classroom, assessment of co-scholastic aspect ,lack of coordination among planners, school administration and preparation of report cards. In an articles published in U.News(2011) & Edutracks feb (2011) it was found that a survey was done two years after CBSE introduced CCE system. The report revealed that 67% of the teachers are still struggling with it and 58% have a negative and indifferent approach towards it. These studies are in the conformity with the findings of the present study. Also study conducted by Sonawanea, S (2011), Tarsing, N.et.al (2011), Adam, F. C. (2009), Jett, P. M. (2009) found that the teachers were not properly oriented and they don't know the proper grading system. These studies are in the conformity with the findings of the present study.

Educational Implications

Some of the main implications of the present study are as follows:

- This study was an attempt to bring out the ground realities of evaluation reforms in schools. It identified the major problems that the school teachers encountered while executing this scheme of evaluation.
- The study was able to elucidate the suggestions and the remedial measures from the teachers to overcome the problems that come in the way of proper execution of evaluation reforms.
- The study can further help the state and the school administration to identify the major problems that the teachers encounter in the classes during executing this scheme and take up the appropriate steps in the areas where teachers seek help.
- The study revealed that there is an immense need to provide adequate training for the teachers the benefits of this system effectively.

- The study highlighted that the teachers should also be provided ample material and professional support for effective implementation of present evaluation scheme in Haryana.
- So still a lot of efforts need to be put in to improve the status and effectiveness of the evaluation system in education. Serious measures should be taken to overcome the barriers which are hindering in the effective implementation of present evaluation system in Haryana.

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